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“IDENTIFICATION AND EVALUATION OF DRUG RELATED PROBLEMS AND ITS PREVALENCE IN MEDICAL AND EMERGENCY WARD OF ATERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL”

D.Amrutha, Johnson Feba, Mathew Nissy, Sam.K.Gloria *

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

According to the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe Foundation (PCNE) classification, “A Drug-Related Problems (DRPs) is an event or circumstance involving drug therapy that actually or potentially interferes with desired health outcomes.” DRPs might result in reduced quality of life, prolonged hospital stay and even raises the risk of morbidity and mortality. A clinical pharmacist plays a significant role in reviewing the prescriptions for drug-related problems. This in turn provides a channel for clinical intervention, thereby improving patient’s quality of care. The prospective, observational, Interventional study focused to identify, evaluate and study the prevalence of drug related problems in medical and emergency unit of a tertiary care teaching hospital. A total of 202 cases was analyzed for DRPs, in which males were prominent 58.91% than females 41.09%. In this study, patients of age group 41-60 years (39.60%) were prevailing. Out of 202 cases, 182 cases were identified with DRP and 20 cases without DRPs. Drug-Drug interactions (67.13%) were the top ranking DRP. Loop diuretics were the common class of drugs involved in DRPs. There was an association between age, poly-pharmacy and length of hospital stay with DRPs. The prevalence of DRP was 90.10%. Interventions were proposed for every DRPs identified. This study demonstrates the importance of clinical pharmacy services in enhancing patient’s health care by decreasing the frequency of occurrence of drug related problems.

Corresponding author

Dr. Gloria. K. Sam

Assistant Professor

Department of Pharmacy Practice

Bapuji Pharmacy College

Davangere -577004

Karnataka, India

+919663073100

gloria_sam52@yahoo.com

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INTRODUCTION

Drugs are the absolute therapeutic tools used in diseased conditions in hospitalized individuals. They are intended to cure, prevent or diagnose diseases, signs and symptoms, but the dark side is that inappropriate use can be the cause of patient morbidity. [1] A drug can easily be the root cause of a serious injury to health or even mortality. Hence safety, appropriateness and effectiveness of drug therapy should be made sure in patient care and even mortality. In order to achieve a quality health care service, inappropriate use of drugs should be identified and resolved. [2] Clinical pharmacy is a health discipline in which pharmacists work in collaboration with other health care professionals to promote rational medication use, which is safe, appropriate and cost-effective use of medications. The responsibility of clinical pharmacy practice aimed at optimizing the drug therapy outcomes while rectifying the detected problems in drug utilization. [12]

Pharmaceutical Care is defined as, "the responsible provision of drug therapy for the purpose of achieving definite therapeutic outcome that improves the patient's quality of life". To achieve an optimized patient outcome in pharmacy practice, the pharmaceutical care should focus mainly on identifying, preventing, and resolving the drug-related problems.

Pharmaceutical care involves three major outcomes:

- a. Recognizing potential and actual medication-related problems,
- b. Resolving actual medication-related problems and
- c. Eradicating potential medication-related problems [1]

According to Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe Foundation (PCNE), Drug-Related Problems are defined as "A Drug-Related Problem is an event or circumstance involving drug therapy that actually or potentially interferes with desired health outcomes. [1] An actual problem has resulted in clinical manifestations like adverse drug reaction or therapy failure due to incorrect dosage. A potential problem is not manifest, but if left unresolved, it may lead to drug-related harm to the patient. [4] Types of DRPs include untreated indication, sub therapeutic dosage, overdose, adverse drug reaction, improper drug selection, drug interaction, drug use without indication. A high number of prescribed medications, poor medication adherence and frequent dosage changes may also contribute to drug-related morbidity and related problems. [16]

Classifying DRPs are important in documentation in clinical practice and research by Clinical pharmacist. The PCNE classification for DRPs is evaluated and updated regularly and there are different versions released. [12]

Prevalence is a statistical concept referring to the number of cases of a disease that are present in a particular population at a given time. Prevalence will determine a person's likelihood of having the disease.

Prevalence = Number of existing cases of a specific period / Number of people in the population during this period.

A clinical intervention is the process of a pharmacist determining and accomplishing a recommendation to attempt to prevent or resolve DRPs. Outcomes of clinical interventions include health related quality of life, patient satisfaction and medication appropriateness. [3] Many studies have proven the significance of pharmacist role in identifying and resolving potential DRPs through timely interventions. [5] The identification of patient at risk and an accurate management of their drug therapy are important challenges for the health care professional to avoid serious clinical consequences caused by Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR). There is a need to reduce economic and medical burdens caused by DRPs by their identification, prevention and solution in a process of pharmaceutical care. It would be much better to prevent drug therapy problems than to correct them, but this is not always possible because of the complexity of pharmacotherapy and the behavior of medicine. [23]

Drug related problems are common among hospitalized patients. DRPs may lead to decreased quality of life, expanded hospital stay, overall health care cost and even risk of morbidity and mortality. [3, 4] Hospitalized patients are more likely exposed to poly-pharmacy. This in turn is a concern for potential DRPs. Several studies conducted in different countries show a high incidence of DRP among hospitalized patients. However, studies show that a greater part of the DRP (50-80%) are often anticipated and pharmaceutical services can decrease the number of ADRs, the length of hospital stay and the cost of care. [3] The study will also help in influencing the development of appropriate policies, plans and intervention programs for the prevention and management of DRPs. [2]

Hence this project was delineated to identify, evaluate, and study the prevalence of DRPs in the Medical and Emergency unit of a tertiary care teaching hospital. This in turn provides a channel for clinical intervention, thereby improving the quality of care for patients admitted in the hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A prospective, observational and Interventional study was carried out in the general medicine and emergency department of a tertiary care hospital. A total of 200 subjects was analyzed during the study. Patient data and prescription details were recorded and analyzed accordingly. DRPs were found out and the clinical pharmacist interventions were proposed to the clinical team in an attempt to anticipate and/or rectify drug-related problems.

Materials used:

- Informed Consent Form
- Patient Data Collection Form

Study Site and design

This is a Prospective observational and Interventional study conducted in the medicine and emergency ward of a tertiary care hospital in Davangere

Study Duration

The Study was conducted for a period of six months.

Study Criteria

The study will be carried out by considering the following inclusion and exclusion Criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients of either sex aged above 18years of age.
- The patient admitted for more than 2 days in medicine or emergency ward.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who are treated from outpatient department and who do not require a hospital stay.
- Patients who are not willing to give informed consent to participate in the study.
- Poisoning related cases.
- Patients with missing and insufficient data.
- Patients prescribed with less than 4 drugs.

Source of Data

The data were collected from the prescriptions of inpatients who are admitted in the medical ward or emergency unit for more than two days.

Study Procedure

A data collection form was prepared which contain details of patient characteristics, physical examination, laboratory result, prevailing medication, comorbidities, length of hospitalization and compatible previous medical and medication histories. The collected data from the patient profile was then being categorized, assessed and analyzed for following parameters:

1. Identifying the most common drugs and drug classes involved in drug related problems.
2. Evaluating the drug related problems.
3. Identifying the predictors of the occurrence of DRPs.
4. Reporting the intervention.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20.0 (IBM). The Chi-squared test was used to determine the association of patient's characteristics and other variables. The t-test was used to compare mean between groups for continuous data. Logistic regression was used to assess the risk factors. Predictiveness of various factors was assessed using Binary Logistic Regression analysis.

Ethical issues:

The ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

RESULTS

After proper examination, using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A total of 202 patients were enrolled in the study.

Table1: Gender wise distribution of patients.

SL.NO	GENDER	FREQUENCY (N=202)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	FEMALE	83	41.09%
2	MALE	119	58.91%
	TOTAL	202	100%

A total of 202 patient case sheets was scrutinized during the study period out of which 58.91% were males and the rest 41.09% were females.

Table 2: Distribution of cases with respect to age group.

Sl.NO	Age (Years)	Frequency (n=202)	Percentage (%)	Mean±SD
1	19-40	52	25.74%	52.40 ± 16.98
2	41-60	80	39.61%	
3	>60	70	34.65%	
	Total	202	100%	

Out of 202 patients enrolled, the majority of subjects were under the age group of 41-60 years 80 (39.60%) followed by above 60 years 70 (34.65%), 19-40 years 52 (25.74%).

Table 3: Distribution of Length of Hospitalization.

Sl.NO	LENGTH OF HOSPITALSTAY (DAYS)	NO.OFPATIENTS (N=202)	PERCENTAGE (%)	MEAN ± SD
1	2 to 5	92	45.54%	6.06 ± 2.21
2	6 to 9	93	46.04%	
3	>9	17	8.42%	

By analyzing the data, we found that the majority of patients stayed for 6-9 days 93 (46.04%) followed by 2-5 days 92 (45.54%), >9 days 17 (8.42%).

Table 4: Distribution of co-morbidities.

Sl.NO	CO-MORBIDITIES	FREQUENCY (N=202)	PERCENTAGE (%)	MEAN±SD
1	0	55	27.3%	1.25±1.14
2	1	82	40.5%	
3	2	38	18.8%	
4	3	17	8.4%	
5	4	7	3.5%	
6	5	3	1.5%	

The patients were categorized based on co- morbidities present to them. Maximum patients were found to have one co-morbidity 82 (40.5%).

Table 5: Distribution of drugs prescribed per prescription.

Sl.NO	POLY-PHARMACY	NUMBER OF CASES (N=202)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Major	85	42.08%
2	Minor	117	57.92%

Out of 202 cases, 117 cases (57.92%) were observed with minor poly-pharmacy and 85 cases (42.08%) were observed with major poly-pharmacy.

Table 6: Distribution of Cases with and without DRPs.

Sl.NO		MALE (%)	FEMALE (%)	TOTAL CASES (N =202)
1	Case with DRPs	107 (88.24)	75 (90.36)	182 (90.10)
2	Case without DRPs	12 (11.76)	8 (9.64)	20 (9.90)

Out of 202 cases, 182 cases were identified with DRPs and 20 without DRPs. Among 182 cases 107 (88.24%) were males and 75 (90.36%) were females.

Table 7: Categorization of different Drug Related Problems.

SI.NO	TYPES OF DRP	NO. OF DRP (N=785)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	ADR	15	1.91%
2	Drug-Drug Interactions	527	67.13%
3	Drug Choice Problems	200	25.48%
4	Dosing Problems	43	5.48%

A total of 785 Drug related problems were obtained from 182 cases. Possible Drug-Drug interactions was the top ranking Drug related problem 527 (67.13%) followed by Drug choice problems 200 (25.48%), Dosing problems 43 (5.48%) and ADR 15 (1.91%).

Table 8: Distribution of Drug-Drug interaction according to degree of severity.

SI.NO	TYPE OF DRUG INTERACTION	NO. OF DRUG INTERACTION(N=527)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Major	36	6.83%
2	Moderate	320	60.72%
3	Minor	171	32.45%

A total of 527 drug interactions were obtained from 182 cases. From these 36 (6.83%) were of major severity, 320 (60.72%) were of moderate severity and 171 (32.45%) were of minor severity.

Table 9: Potential drug- drug interactions (n = 36).

SI.NO	INTERACTING DRUGS	EFFECT	SEVERITY	NO. OF PATIENTS (%)
1	Azithromycin+Ondansetron	Both increase Q_t_c interval	Major	8(22.22%)
2	Ofloxacin+Ondansetron	Both increase Q_t_c interval	Major	3(8.33%)
3	Rabeprazole+Clopidogrel	Decreases effects of Clopidogrel	Major	2(5.56%)
4	Linezolid+Tramadol	Both increases Serotonin level	Major	2(5.56%)
5	AluminiumHydroxide+Ofloxacin	Decreases levels of Ofloxacin	Major	1(2.78%)
6	Azithromycin+Enoxaparin	Increases effect of Enoxaparin	Major	1(2.78%)
7	Cefpodoxime+Heparin	Increases the effects of Heparin	Major	1(2.78%)
8	Ceftriaxone+Heparin	Increases the effect of Heparin	Major	1(2.78%)
9	Ceftriaxone+Warfarin	Increases the effect of Warfarin	Major	1(2.78%)
10	Clarithromycin+Ondansetron	Both increase Q_t_c interval	Major	1(2.78%)
11	Doxycycline+Amoxicillin	Decreases the effect of Amoxicillin	Major	1(2.78%)
12	Ferrous Gluconate+Doxycycline	Decreases the level of Doxycycline	Major	1(2.78%)
13	Fluconazole+Clopidogrel	Decreases the effect of Clopidogrel	Major	1(2.78%)
14	Fluconazole+Ondansetron	Increase Q_t_c interval	Major	1(2.78%)
15	Hydrocortisone+Tolvaptan	Decreases the effect of Tolvaptan	Major	1(2.78%)
16	Ketoconazole+Dexamethasone	Increases the effect of Dexamethasone	Major	1(2.78%)
17	Labetalol+Metoprolol	Both increases anti Hypertensive Channel Blocking	Major	1(2.78%)
18	Nortriptyline+Fluconazole	Both increase Q_t_c Interval	Major	1(2.78%)
19	Pipercillin+Enoxaparin	Increases the effect of Enoxaparin	Major	1(2.78%)
20	Quetiapine+Levodopa	Decreases the effect of Levodopa	Major	1(2.78%)
21	Ranitidine+Ketoconazole	Decreases the effect of Ketoconazole	Major	1(2.78%)
22	Rifampicin+Hydrocortisone	Decreases the effect of Hydrocortisone	Major	1(2.78%)
23	Rifampicin+Pyrazinamide	Increases toxicity of other	Major	1(2.78%)
24	Diltiazem+Amlodipine	Diltiazem increases the level or effect of Amlodipine	Major	1(2.78%)
25	Octreotide+Ondansetron	Both increases Q_t level	Major	1(2.78%)

As per our study potential drug interaction were frequently observed between Azithromycin-Ondansetron (22.22%) followed by Ofloxacin-Ondansetron (8.33%) and Rabeprazole-Clopidogrel (5.56%).

Table10: Types of Drug Choice Problem.

SI.NO	TYPES OF DRUG CHOICE PROBLEM	NO. OF DRUG CHOICE PROBLEM(N=200)	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	Inappropriate drug	93	46.50%
2	Duplication of therapeutic group	11	5.50%
3	Contraindication	36	18.00%
4	Treatment without indication	30	15.00%
5	Untreated condition	30	15.00%

Out of 200 drug choice problems, 93 (46.50%) were of Inappropriate drug followed by 36 (18%) Contraindication 30 (15%) treatment without indication, 30 (15%) Untreated Condition, 11 (5.50%) Duplication of therapeutic groups.

Table 11: Categorization of dosing problems.

SI.NO	TYPE OF DOSING PROBLEM	NO. OF DOSING PROBLEM(N=43)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	High Dose	16	37.21%
2	Low Dose	3	6.98%
3	Duration of Treatment	24	55.81%

Out of 43 dosing problem duration of treatment 24 (55.81%) was more prominent followed by high dose 16 (37.21%) and low doses 3 (6.98%).

Table 12: Identified cases of suspected Adverse Drug Reactions.

SI.NO	CLASS	DRUG	ADR	NO. OF PATIENTS(N=15)	PERCENTAGE
1	Mucolytics	Acetylcysteine	Nausea And Vomiting	1	6.67%
2	Cephalosporin	Cefixime	Mouth Ulcer	1	6.67%
3	Cephalosporin	Cefotaxime	Maculopapular Rash	1	6.67%
4	Cephalosporin	Ceftriaxone	Maculopapular Rash	2	13.33%
5	Cephalosporin	Cefuroxime	Maculopapular Rash	1	6.67%
6	Tetracycline	Doxycycline	Generalized Erythematous Rash	1	6.67%
7	Female Gonad Hormone	Oestrogen	Galactorrhoea	1	6.67%
8	Vitamin Supplement	Multivitamin	Urticaria	1	6.67%
9	Proton Pump Inhibitor	Omeprazole	Angioedema	1	6.67%
10	Vitamin Supplement	Optineuron	Itching	1	6.67%
11	Hydantoin	Phenytoin	Stevens- Johnson Syndrome	1	6.67%
12	Beta Blocker	Propranolol	Hypoglycaemia	1	6.67%
13	Coumarin Derivative	Warfarin	Coagulopathy	1	6.67%
14	Cephalosporin	Ceftriaxone	Hypersensitivity	1	6.67%

Among 15 ADRs, most frequent ADRs were identified in patients prescribed with cephalosporins (n=6) followed by mucolytics, tetracycline, vitamin supplement, female gonad hormone, PPI, hydantoin, beta blocker, coumarin derivatives.

Table 13: Most common drug and drug classes involved in DRP.

SI.NO	DRUG	DRUG CLASS	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
1	Furosemide	Loop Diuretics	52	7.41%
2	Pantoprazole	Proton Pump Inhibitor	44	6.27%
3	Insulin	Insulin	29	4.13%
4	Ceftriaxone	Cephalosporin	26	3.70%
5	Ondansetron	5-HT ₃ receptor antagonist	26	3.70%
6	Doxycycline	Tetracycline	22	3.13%
7	Telmisartan	Angiotensin ₂ receptor blocker	18	2.56%
8	Acetaminophen	NSAIDs	16	2.28%
9	Cefuroxime	Cephalosporin	15	2.14%
10	Hydrocortisone	Corticosteroids	15	2.14%

Table 13 shows that Loop diuretics were the most common drug class involved in the DRPs followed by Proton Pump Inhibitor(PPI), Insulin, Cephalosporin, 5-HT₃ Receptor Antagonist, Tetracycline, Angiotensin Receptors Blocker, Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs(NSAIDs), Corticosteroids.

Table14: Potentially inappropriate drugs prescribed as per Beers Criteria, 2015.

Sl.NO	DRUGS	FREQUEN CY	CONCERN
1	Benzodiazepines Alprazolam Clonazepam	1 1	Older adults have increased sensitivity to benzodiazepines and decreased metabolism of long-acting agents; in general, all benzodiazepines increase risk of cognitive impairment, delirium, falls, fractures, and motor vehicle crashes in older adults.
	Chlordiazepoxide	1	
2	Firstgeneration antihistamines Chlorpheniramine Diphenhydramine	2 1	
3	NSAIDs Aspirin Diclofenac	1 2	Increased risk of gastrointestinal bleeding or peptic ulcer disease in higher-risk groups, including those aged > 75 or taking oral or parenteral Corticosteroids, anticoagulants or antiplatelet agents; use of Proton-Pump Inhibitor or Misoprostol reduces but does not eliminate risk.
	Mefenamic Acid	1	
4	Diuretics Furosemide Torsemide Spironolactone	14 3 1	
5	Others Prazosin	3	
	Nitrofurantoin	1	
	Pregabalin Trihexyphenidyl	1 1	High risk of orthostatic hypotension; not recommended as routine treatment for hypertension; alternative agents have superior risk. Potential for Pulmonary toxicity, Hepato toxicity and peripheral neuropathy, Especially with long-term use; safer alternatives available/ benefit profile. CNS adverse effects Not recommended for prevention of extra pyramidal symptoms with antipsychotics; more effective agents available for treatment of Parkinson Disease.
	Levetiracetam	1	
	Nifedipine	2	CNS adverse effects.
	Warfarin	1	Potential for hypertension risk of precipitating myocardial ischemia.
	Metoclopramide	2	Increased risk of bleeding if given with NSAIDs.
	Clonidine	1	Can cause extra pyramidal effects, including tardive dyskinesia ; risk may be greater in frail older adults .
	Liquid paraffin	2	Higher risk of adverse CNS effects; may cause bradycardia and orthostatic hypotension; not recommended as routine treatment for hypertension.
	Insulin	12	Potential for aspiration and adverse effects; safer alternative available .
	Enoxaparin	1	Higher risk of hypoglycaemia without improvement in hyperglycaemia management regardless of care setting.
			Increased risk of bleeding.

Figure 1: Prevalence of Drug Related problems.

DRPs were found in 90.10% of the study subjects. A total of 785 DRPs were identified from 182 patients during the study period.

Table 15: Acceptance of recommendation according to drug involved in DRP.

SI.NO	Acceptance of Intervention	No. of cases (n=182)	Percentage (%)
1	Suggestion accepted therapy changed	45	24.73%
2	Suggestion accepted but therapy not changed	80	43.95%
3	Neither suggestion accepted nor therapy Changed	57	31.32%

For every possible drug related problems found in the prescription, appropriate intervention were advised from the investigators part as well as provision for the physician to review and initiate a modification of his choice. Interventions were provided for 182 cases, of which suggestion accepted therapy changed were found to be predominant 80 (43.95%) followed by suggestion accepted therapy changed 45 (24.73%), neither suggestion accepted nor therapy changed 57 (31.32%).

Table16: Associated factors for the occurrence of DRPs.

SI.NO	Variable	Category	DRPs		Total	Odds Ratio (95%CI)	P Value
			Yes (N=182)	No (N=20)			
1	Gender	Male	107(58.79)	12 (60)	119	0.902 (0.320 - 2.543)	0.856
		Female	75(41.21)	8 (40)	83		
2	Age	19-40	45(24.73)	7 (35)	52	3.309 (0.741 - 14.770)	0.076
		41-60	66 (36.26)	10 (50)	76	3.586 (0.901 - 14.274)	P<0.043
		>60	71 (39.01)	3 (15)	74	1.0	
3	Length Of Hospital Stay (Days)	2-5	82 (45.05)	10 (50)	92	0.537 (0.086 - 3.353)	.797
		6-9	85 (46.70)	8 (40)	93	0.505 (0.081 - 3.143)	.823
		>9	15 (8.24)	2 (10)	17	1.0	
		< 10	102 (56.04)	15 (75)	117	2.533 (0.782 - 8.203)	.148
4	No. of drugs	≥10	80 (43.96)	5 (25)	85	1.0	
		0	45(24.73)	10(50)	55	1.0	
5	Comorbidity	1	76(41.76)	6(30)	82	0.444 (0.037 - 5.395)	.999
		2	36(19.78)	2(10)	38	0.158 (0.012 - 2.003)	.999
		3	17(9.34)	0	17	0.111 (0.007 - 1.811)	.999
		4	6 (3.30)	1(10)	7	0.000 (0.000)	
		5	2(1.10)	1(10)	3	0.333 (0.014 - 8.182)	.999

The identification of risk factors for DRPs may be useful in finding patients at risk. Gender, age, length of hospital stay, number of drugs, number of co morbidities were analyzed to determine whether they could predict the occurrence of DRPs or not. Age was shown to be a risk factor for the occurrence of DRPs while gender, length of hospital stay, number of drugs and number of co-morbidities were not. Patients belonging to the age group 41-60 are 3.6 times more likely to develop drug related problem as compared to patients belonging to the age group >60.

Table17: Comparison of factors and occurrence of adverse reactions and Drug interactions.

Sl.NO	Factors		Adverse reactions		P value	Drug interactions		P value
			Yes	No		Yes	No	
1	Elderly	Yes	6	75	0.999	66	15	0.119
		No	9	112				
2	Poly-pharmacy	Yes	2	83	P<0.019	76	9	P<0.000
		No	13	104				
3	Length of stay	2-5	4	88	0.298	64	28	0.129
		6-9	9	84				
		>9	2	15				
4	Co morbidity	0	3	52	0.573	44	11	0.559
		1	5	77				
		2	3	35				
		3	3	14				
		4	1	6				
5	Gender	5	0	3	0.929	3	0	0.533
		Male	9	110				
		Female	6	77				

The parameter poly-pharmacy had a positive result of ADR ($p < 0.019$) and Drug interaction ($p < 0.000$).

Table 18: Comparison of factors and occurrence of Dosing Problem and Drug Choice problem.

Sl.NO	Factors		Drug Choice problem		P value	Dosing problems		P value
			Yes	No		Yes	No	
1	Elderly	Yes	57	24	P<0.000	9	72	0.075
		No	44	77				
2	Poly-pharmacy	Yes	52	33	P<0.007	20	65	P<0.030
		No	49	68				
3	Length of stay	2-5	43	49	0.601	23	69	P<0.001
		6-9	48	45				
		>9	10	7				
4	Comorbidity	0	32	23	0.436	10	45	0.978
		1	41	41				
		2	15	23				
		3	9	8				
		4	2	5				
5	Gender	5	2	1	0.668	1	2	0.129
		Male	61	58				
		Female	40	43				

The elderly had a positive statistical association with Drug Choice problem ($p < 0.000$). Also there were significant association between poly-pharmacy and Drug Choice Problem ($p < 0.007$) or dosing problem ($p < 0.030$). In addition length of hospitalization was found to be associated with Dosing Problem ($p < 0.001$).

Table 19: Comparison of with & without DRPs in relation to other variables.

VARIABLES		DRPS				STATISTICAL ANALYSIS	
SI.NO		YES (N=182)		NO (N=20)		UNPAIRED T TEST	
		MEAN	STD DEVIATION	MEAN	STD DEVIATION	T VALUE	P VALUE
1	Age	53.31	17.04	44.10	14.28	2.33	P<0.021
2	Days of stay	6.04	2.09	6.55	2.67	-0.998	0.32
3	No of Co- morbidity	1.28	1.10	0.95	1.39	1.24	0.22
4	No of drugs	9.50	2.98	8.45	2.68	1.51	0.13

Mean age of patients with DRP were 53.31 and without DRP were 44.10. There is a mean difference between two groups and this difference is statistically significant. Higher the age, chances of occurrence of DRPs was more.

DISCUSSION

In our study, out of 202 patients, 119 (58.91%) patients were males and 83 (41.09%) patients were females. This study revealed male predominance over female as similar to a study conducted by Dinesh R et al, Satish BP et al.[1,3]The present study revealed that the patients belonging to the age group of 41-60 years 80 (39.61%) were more predominant which is in compliance with the study conducted by JavedhShareef et al.[17]In our study, majority of the patients have 1 co-morbidity 82 (40.5%) followed by patient having no co- morbidity 55 (27.3%) which was found to correspond to the study conducted by Celin A.T et al.[14]Minor poly-pharmacy was common among hospitalized patients as 117 (57.92%) of the study patients were given 5-9 drugs during the hospital stay, followed by major poly-pharmacy. This observation eventuates with the study conducted by Mohammed Biset et al.[2]

The drug interactions 527 (67.13%) were the most predominant Drug-related problems followed by drug choice problems 200 (25.48%), dosing problem 43 (5.48%), ADR 15(1.91%). The findings were similar to study conducted by Sarfaraz Mohammed et al.[19] A total of 527 drug interactions were observed in 182 patients. Majority of drug interactions were of moderate severity 320 (60.72%) followed by interactions of minor significance 171(32.45%) and then major significance 36 (6.83%).This coincides with the study performed by A. Chandrakanth et al.[15]The most conventional drug choice problems was found to be inappropriate drug 93(46.50%) followed by contraindications 36 (18%), TWI 30 (15%), UI 30 (15%) and Duplication of therapeutic group 11 (5.50%). This result is persistent with the study conducted by JainafNachiya.R.A.M et al.[7]The most commonly found dosing problems was found to be duration of treatment24 (55.81%) followed by high dose 16 (37.21%) and low dose 3 (6.98%). This was similar to the study performed by JainafNachiya.R.A.M. et al.[7]

The most found ADR was caused by drug class Cephalosporin (n =6, 40.01%). This was in contrast to the result obtained by study conducted by Dinesh R et al in which more frequent ADR was found to be caused by beta lactam antibiotics.[1]In the present study, the therapeutic agents most commonly involved in DRPs include Furosemide (52), Pantoprazole (44), Insulin (29) and Ceftriaxone (26). This is equivalent to the study conducted by JavedhShareef et al. [17]

The most frequent intervention provided by pharmacist was suggestion accepted but therapy not changed 80 (43.95%). The observation correlates with study conducted by A. Chandrakanth et al.[15] The prevalence of Drug related Problems was found to be 182 (90.10%). This coincides with the study conducted by Mamunuwa et al which shows the prevalence of 92%. [12] Potentially inappropriate drug use in elderly was assessed by Beers criteria which comprise a list of medication that poses potential risks outweighing potential benefits. A total of 23 drugs as per Beers criteria were found to have been used inappropriately. Among which use of furosemide was most common and showed the potential risk to alleviate hyponatremia followed by insulin which showed the potential risk of hypoglycaemia. This result obtained was contrast to the study conducted by Ogbonna B. O et al in which promethazine occurred as high severity, followed by pentazocine and diazepam respectively. [9]

In the attempt to recognize the risk factors associated with the occurrence of DRPs, the study showed that the age is an important risk factor for DRPs, where as gender, length of hospital stay, number of drugs and number of co-morbidities did not have significant association with the occurrence of DRPs. The result obtained was analogous to study conducted by Diana.M. Rydberg et al. [21] This study is in contradiction with the study conducted by Mohammed Biset et al, in which number of drugs prescribed per patient is an important risk factor for DRPs.[2] Similarly the study in Jimma by Tigabu et al did not show significant association between the likelihood of DRP occurrence and length of hospital stay and number of co morbidity.[13]

Comparison between factors and occurrence of DPRs were identified. The elderly had a positive statistical association with Drug Choice problems (p< 0.000) and poly-pharmacy had a positive statistical association with Drug interaction (p<0.000). This observation is in support with the study conducted by HasnizaZamanHuri et al. [6] Comparison of patients with and without DRPs in relation to other variables was observed. Mean age of patient with DRP were 53.31 and without DRP were 44.10. There is a mean difference between two groups and this difference is statistically significant. Higher the age, chances of occurrence of DRPs were more. For other variables there is no mean difference.

CONCLUSION

Drug Related Problems are frequent in hospitalized patients. Most of the studies demonstrate that majority of DRP (50-80%) are precluded and pharmaceutical services can diminish the number of DRPs, the length of hospitalization and the cost of healthcare. In the study determined the high prevalence of drug related problems (90.10%) among the patients receiving treatment. Out of 202 patients, 182 DRPs were recognized in which drug interactions (527) most prominent were accompanied by drug choice problems (200), dosing problems (43), and ADR (15). Potentially inappropriate drug prescribed for elderly patients were determined by Beers criteria. A total of 23 drugs as per Beers criteria were observed to be used inappropriately. In our study there was a chief association between age, poly-pharmacy, and length of hospital stay with DRP. Our study submits the significant need for clinical pharmacy services in better management of diseases in order to bring down the number of DRPs and to improve quality of life. Although this study emphasizes on the importance of clinical pharmacy services to bring down the incidence of DRPs, further research is recommended.

ABBREVIATION

SL NO	ABBREVIATION	DETAILS
01	ADR	Adverse Drug Reaction
02	DRP	Drug Related Problems
03	NSAIDs	Non- Steroidal Anti inflammatory Drugs
04	PCNE	Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe
05	PPI	Proton Pump Inhibitor
06	SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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